

EACD Bruges 2024

Book of

Abstracts

36th Annual Meeting of the European
Academy of Childhood Disability

ID: 334 / 100-P: 10

Abstract submission

Scientific Poster

Topics: HW&P: Diversity, equity and inclusion

Contributions to conception/design: No

Contributions to analysis/interpretation: No

Contributions to draft/revision: No

Contributions as (co-)author: No

Inclusion of specially abled children in the regular schools: Did we miss something?

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Introduction: The goal of including specially abled children in regular schools is to give these children a chance to socialize. It can potentially help in building relationships with children without disabilities and create a better environment overall. In most cases, their schoolmates have a neutral attitude toward them, but it also happens quite often that they are met with negative attitudes and teasing. In worst cases even bullying can occur.

Aim of this study was to find out to what extent are specially abled children exposed to bullying in schools from their point of view.

Participants and methods: 22 children with cerebral palsy, GMFCS level I, II or III, aged 7 to 14 years were included in the study. They answered 6 simple questions on their own: Have you ever had an argument with schoolmate? Have you ever told someone at school that you would hurt him? Have you ever attacked someone at school? Are you afraid of other children at school? Do they make fun of you? Do they bully you?

Results: Three children (13%) reported that they had an argument with schoolmate (few times). Fifteen children (68%) reported that they have been teased very often and 11 (50%) reported that they have been bullied sometime.

Conclusion: The best way to gain insight into the school lives of the specially abled children is to let them speak and listen to them. This can guide us better in our attempts to improve their health and wellbeing.